

Role of Library Media Centre in promotion of Reading Habits, ICT skills and creativity among its users: A study with reference to KV Bilaspur

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Abstract

This research paper examines the role of “Library Media Centre (LMC)” in the “Promotion of Reading Habits, ICT Skills and Creativity” among students and teachers with reference to Kendriya Vidyalaya Bilaspur (KVS RO Raipur Region). The inculcation of reading habits, enhancement in ICT Skills and creativity among users have been analysed and presented in the form of diagram. The various online and offline activities of libraries have also been listed and explained.

The present study was conducted using class room interactions and telephonic method with the students. The instructional and interview pattern was designed for the purpose of data collection and the same were conducted personally on randomly basis to the students of Vidyalaya. A total 732 students were interacted and telephonically contacted; out of which 706 were answered back (96.44%). Results of the findings were interpreted using simple percentages and organized in tables, and charts for clarity and better comprehension.

The results of the findings revealed that students have good reading habits and further enhanced their ICT Skills and creativity. The suggestions on promotion of reading habits have also been incorporated.

Keywords: Reading habits, Kendriya Vidyalaya Bilaspur, Library Media Centre, e-granthalaya, Information and Communication Technology, Wakelet Profile

Introduction

School Library is a key feature of a Vidyalaya and constitute a centre entity. It is indeed “Heart” of Vidyalaya, hence it should preferable be located at the centre of the Vidyalaya. A library indeed plays very vital role in “Promotion of Reading Habits among its users”. School library and its services help its users to enhance their creativity and ICT skills. Normally users of school library include students, teachers, other staff members, authorities of Vidyalaya. The sources and services of Vidyalaya library play significant role in the inculcation of reading habits among its users. Now a days school library also plays vital role in creation of learning space for its users as per their information demand. A proper Annual Library Activity Plan helps to execute the services of library throughout the academic session.

The library of Kendriya Vidyalaya Bilaspur is a resourceful and executes its services in a hybrid way. It is fully automated using latest e-granthalaya 4.0 software of NIC New Delhi. During recent Pandemic library services played very vital role in

implementing online education in which students involved in teaching learning process from home. A survey was conducted to know the interest of different types of users of library. This survey helped to analyse the level of “promotion of reading habits, creativity, ICT skills” took place through the initiatives of e-library services of KV Bilaspur.

Reading is oftenly considered as a complex activity with various benefits and is the key for lifelong success and ensures development of children.

New format to promote reading: Digital way

New format i.e., digital way enables users to retrieve information very quickly, pinpointedly and comprehensively. A proper strategy is required in order to implement it. During the ongoing pandemic, academic institution pays much attention towards strengthening and allocating more funds in annual budget for digital acquisitions. In future the printed word will likely to be converted to electronic form and subsequently will be opening the new arena of promotional avenues for reading habits. There is a need to strengthen Audio-Visual and Computer-the based materials in order to facilitate the digital services.

Library Services and sources for the promotion of Reading Habits at KV Bilaspur

1	Detailed report of activities conducted to inculcate reading habits
	<p>1. Library Services in a Hybrid Ways and through celebrations of National Library events such as 100 days Reading Campaign, Pustakopkar, National Digital Reading Day-week-month in June-July every year, National Librarian's Day on 12th August in memory of Father of Library Science in India - Dr S R Ranganathan and National Library week from 14-20 November every year. Promotion of Reading Habits through users' requisitions, through Library 2.0 Services, Digital Library services such as Wakelet Profile, Web Blogs, Mobile Library, subscription of e-granthalaya 4.0, theme based virtual Libraries, certificate-based e-quizzes. Books and Magazine Reviews, importance of Newspaper reading. Student's Creativity – Book Mark, Book Jacket and Scrap Book and library note books by the students</p> <p>2. Student's creativity such as book mark, theme based scrap books, book jacket</p> <p>Quality Collection development during the academic session. Links enclosed https://100daysreadingcampaignkvbilaspur.blogspot.com/</p>

Here are some simple tips to attract you towards reading.

1. Regular reading a must. ...
2. Read before your groups, family as per your interest. ...
3. Frequent visit to offline and online library and read. ...
4. Create a reading space and library as a alternative learning class room
5. Reading as per his/her desire
6. Search for reading moments in everyday life. ...
7. Re-read liked books and/or magazines. ...
8. Learn more about methods of reading.

Objectives Of The Study

This study is intended to achieve the following objectives:

1. To examine the amount of time students, spend in reading.
2. To identify the quality collection development for school library
3. To examine the preference of library collection and activities by students.
4. To know the existing offline and online utilities are adequate.
5. To know the role of library resources and services in enhancing the Reading Habits among its users
6. To know the role of Library Media Centre in the enhancement and meaningful use of ICT skills along with creativity among the students

Research Questions

1. Have you been provided opportunity to visit library in a hybrid way?
2. Whether the orientation program was conducted?
3. Whether the requisitions of your choice were asked?
4. Whether the existing offline and online e-library materials are adequate?

5. What is the amount of time you spend in reading and purpose for reading?
6. What library collection do the students and teachers prefer?
7. Do you think that library sources and services helped you to enhance your reading habits?
8. The role of Library Media Centre in the enhancement and meaningful use of ICT skills and creativity among the students
9. Overall satisfaction with the existing library sources and services?

Hypothesis

There is a significant relationship with role of LMC and promotion of Reading Habits, ICT skills and Students creativity

Methodology adopted

The present study was conducted using class room interactions and telephonic method with the students. The instructional and interview pattern was designed for the purpose of data collection and the same were conducted personally on randomly basis to the students of Vidyalaya. A total 732 students were interacted and telephonically contacted; out of which 706 were answered back (96.44%). On the basis of mentioned methodology, the data has been analyzed and tabulated. All the results have been presented in the form of tables. For the data analysis percentage technique has been adopted.

The Survey Area

This study is a case study of a selected area. The study is limited to Kendriya Vidyalaya Bilaspur under the jurisdiction of KVS RO Raipur. This study involves students and teachers of KV Bilaspur. The respondents were interacted during classes and interview technique was also utilized.

The Sample Population

To ensure a fair representative sample and effective handling, 732 users i.e students and teachers were sampled for the study through simple random

sampling technique with interactions during their library classes. The sample were taken from students

(classes 4 to 12) along with teachers of Kendriya Vidyalaya Bilaspur.

Data Analysis and Interpretations

1. opportunity to visit library in a hybrid way?

Fig 1. It shows the user getting opportunities to visit Library. Data analysis reveals 100% users agreed that they are getting opportunities to visit

library to satisfy their information desire and promotion of reading habits.

2. Conduction of Orientation Programme

Fig. 2 indicates the conduction of orientation programme by the library teacher. The figure suggests the 98% users have gone through the

orientation programme about the functioning of library and only 2% of users are unaware about it.

3. Requisitions from students and teachers for the development of quality collection

Fig. 3 indicates the data analysis on requisitions in order to develop quality collections. The 688 respondents (97.45%) are agreed with giving their requisitions for

the development of quality collections whereas rest of the users are unaware (2.5%) about it.

4. Adequateness of Library resources

Fig. 4 indicates the adequateness of existing library resources. Respondents agreed on (677, 95.89%) and very few (29, 4%) not sure about it.

5. Amount of time users spend in reading

Fig. 5. It indicates the amount of time users of library spend in reading. It reveals most of the readers spend at least 2 to 3 hours daily (372,

52.6%), 3 to 4 hours (139, 20%) even >4 hours (31 users) where as preferred less than 1 hours (14 users), and some are irregular (61 users).

6. Library Collection and user's Preferences

Fig. 6 refers the preference of Library Collection by the students and teachers. The respondents preferred use and retrieval of all types of resources. As diagram depicts 97%-98% responses prefer

Reference books, Newspapers whereas 92%-93% prefer Magazines, Fiction and Non-fictions. The subject books, and e-resources are liked by 78%-87% respondents. It shows that the respondents

preferred story books, magazines, newspapers, reference books than e-resources.

7. Library Sources and Services enhancing Reading Habits

Fig. 7 shows that library sources and services helped in enhancing reading habits of users of library. The 657 (93%) of respondents are agreed that the existing library sources and services have enabled them to promote their reading habits. Whereas only 49 respondents (7%) are not sure

about it. Hence it depicts that library sources and services play vital role in uplifting the “Reading Habits” among users and it is proved that **there is a significant relationship with role of LMC and promotion of Reading Habits.**

8. The role of Library Media Centre in the enhancement and meaningful use of ICT skills Creativity, among the students

Fig. 8 shows the role of Library Media Centre in the enhancement and meaningful use of ICT skills among the students. Data analysis reveals that majority of the users of library 92% are agreed on enhancement and meaningful use of ICT devices

whereas only 08% of users are not sure about it hence it is satisfied that **there is a significant relationship with role of LMC and enhancement of ICT skills and Students creativity among the students.**

9. Overall satisfaction with the existing library sources and services

Fig. 9 shows Overall satisfaction with the existing library sources and services. The data analysis clearly indicates the (551, 78%) of users are mostly satisfied, (112, 16%) readers are satisfied whereas only (43, 6%) users are neutral.

Findings

The data analysis depicts that the existing library sources and services help immensely in “Uplifting the Reading Habits among Users”. The e-resources ensure meaningful use of ICT devices among the library users. They are also enhancing their ICT skills and creativity. They update and secure information very quickly. They spend quality time in reading and retrieving desired resources. These facilities help their readers to know and place their desired reading materials.

Suggestions

The users of library should attend orientation programme.

User’s feedback should be periodically taken.

Users should frequently share their requisitions in order to develop the quality resources of library media centre.

Network facilities should be strengthened.

Conclusion

The present research survey suggests that the effective collection development with the help of requisitions by the users of library help immensely in the promotion of reading habits. Students and teachers are also accessing e-library for promoting their reading habits and enhancing the creativity, ICT skills.. Users are accessing these services as per their convenient. It has also been seen that academic institution has been given emphasis to allocate more budget towards procuring digital accessories. It can be mentioned that the digital services of library of KV Bilaspur is playing a prominent role to inculcate the “Reading Habits”

among different types of users. It also ensured the meaningful use of these ICT devices by the users very effectively.

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